

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidative regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes by benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate

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Abstract : The oxidative deoxygenation of several aldo- and keto-oximes by benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate (BTMACB) in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water is found to be first order with respect to both oximes and BTMACB. The oxidation of ketoximes is slower than that of aldioximes. The rates of oxidation of aldioximes correlated well in terms of Pavalich-Taft dual substituent-parameter equation. The low positive value of polar reaction constant indicated a nucleophilic attack by a chlorobromate ion on the carbonyl carbon. The reaction is subjected to steric hindrance by the alkyl groups. The effect of solvent composition indicated that the rate increases with an increase in the polarity of the solvent. A mechanism involving the formation of a cyclic activated complex, in the rate-determining step, has been proposed.

Keywords : Oxime, benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate, carbonyl, mechanism, kinetics.

Introduction

Regeneration of carbonyl compounds from its derivatives under mild conditions is an important process in synthetic organic chemistry. Benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate (BTMACB) is one of the quaternary ammonium polyhalides which has been used as an effective halogenating and oxidizing agent in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻³. Polymeric benzyltrimethylammonium dichloroiodate and dibromoiodate have been used for the addition of halogens to olefins⁴. The polyhalides are more suitable than molecular halogens because of their solid nature, ease of handling, stability, selectivity and excellent product yield. A few reports (including BTMACB) regarding the kinetic and mechanistic studies of the reactions of polyhalides are available in the literature⁵⁻⁸. There seems to be no report on the kinetics and mechanism of oxidative deoxygenation of several aldo- and keto-oximes by BTMACB in aqueous acetic acid. Mechanistic aspects have also been discussed.

Experimental

Materials and methods : Oximes were prepared by the reported standard methods⁹ and their m.p. was checked with literature values. BTMACB was also prepared by

the reported method¹. Acetic acid was refluxed with CrO₃ and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then fractionated¹⁰.

Product analysis : The oxidation of the oximes results in the regeneration of corresponding carbonyl compounds, as confirmed by TLC (eluant : CCl₄/Et₂O). The product analyses were carried out by the reported method⁴. Isolation of the product was attempted in the oxidation of oximes of benzaldehyde and acetophenone. In a typical experiment, the oxime (0.2 mol) and BTMACB (0.02 mol) were dissolved in 50 ml of 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid and allowed to stand for ca. 10 h for the completion of the reaction. Silica gel (5 g) was then added to the reaction mixture and the mixture was stirred for 15 min¹¹. It was then filtered and the solid residue was washed with the solvent (2 × 15 ml). The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator and the residue was purified on a silica-gel column (eluant : CCl₄/Et₂O). Evaporation of the solvent afforded the pure carbonyl compound. Yields of benzaldehyde and acetophenone were 1.73 g (81%) and 2.06 g (86%) respectively. The presence of HNO₂ in completely reduced reaction mixtures was confirmed by a positive starch-iodide test¹².

Kinetics measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large

excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the oxime over BTMACB. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (± 0.1 K). The reactions were followed for up to 80% by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of BTMACB at 395 nm spectrophotometrically. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear least squares plots of $\log [\text{BTMACB}]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed the rate constants to be reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. We have used coefficient of determination (R^2 or r^2), standard deviation (sd) and Exner's¹³ parameter, ψ , as the measures of goodness of fit. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was determined from the relation, $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{oxime}]$.

Results and discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the oximes studied. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

Stoichiometry : The analysis of products indicated the following overall reaction,

Rate laws : The reaction is first order with respect to BTMACB. The individual kinetic runs yielded linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots between $\log [\text{BTMACB}]$ and time. Further, the values of k_{obs} do not depend on the initial concentration of BTMACB. The reaction exhibited a linear

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of acetaldoxime by BTMACB at 298 K

$10^3 [\text{BTMACB}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Oxime] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.1	9.18
1.0	0.2	17.8
1.0	0.4	35.1
1.0	0.6	53.6
1.0	0.8	71.0
1.0	1.0	89.1
1.0	1.5	135
0.5	0.8	18.9
2.0	0.8	17.1
3.0	0.8	18.0
4.0	0.8	17.5
5.0	0.8	19.7

dependence on the concentration of the oximes (Table 1). The reaction is first order with respect to oximes also.

Effect of temperature : The rate constants were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Effect of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride/bromide ion : The rates of oxidation were not affected by the addition of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride (BTMACl) or potassium bromide (Table 3).

Effect of solvent composition : The rate of oxidation was determined in solvents containing different amounts of acetic acid and water. It was observed that the rate increased with an increase in the amount of water in the

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of oximes ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{OH}$) by BTMACB

Substituent		$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*
		278 K	288 K	298 K	308 K	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
H	H	1030	1170	1310	1470	18.4 \pm 0.2	-243 \pm 1	78.4 \pm 0.2
H	Me	62.1	89.1	126	180	24.4 \pm 0.3	-203 \pm 1	84.7 \pm 0.3
H	Et	48.6	72.0	99.9	144	24.7 \pm 0.4	-204 \pm 1	85.3 \pm 0.3
H	Pr	27.9	43.2	64.8	99.0	29.5 \pm 0.4	-192 \pm 1	86.5 \pm 0.3
H	Pr ⁱ	20.7	33.3	51.3	80.1	31.7 \pm 0.3	-187 \pm 1	87.2 \pm 0.2
H	ClCH ₂	117	153	189	243	15.8 \pm 0.4	-227 \pm 2	83.4 \pm 0.3
H	Ph	171	252	396	594	29.3 \pm 0.7	-177 \pm 2	82.1 \pm 0.6
Me	Me	3.78	7.02	12.6	22.5	42.7 \pm 0.3	-163 \pm 1	90.9 \pm 0.3
Me	Et	2.97	5.58	10.8	19.8	45.8 \pm 0.6	-154 \pm 2	91.5 \pm 0.4
Et	Et	2.34	4.50	8.82	17.1	48.0 \pm 0.8	-148 \pm 2	92.0 \pm 0.6
Me	Ph	15.3	20.7	26.1	35.1	18.2 \pm 0.5	-236 \pm 2	88.4 \pm 0.4

Table 3. Effect of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride or potassium bromide on the rate of oxidation of acetaldoxime by BTMACB

[BTMACB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [acetaldoxime] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 308 K

10 ³ [BTMACl] or [KBr] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.00	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
<i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹)						
BTMACl	90.7	88.2	91.8	89.0	92.7	87.3
KBr	87.7	92.5	89.1	93.6	90.9	88.2

Table 4. Effect of solvent composition in the oxidation of acetaldoxime by BTMACB

[BTMACB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [acetaldoxime] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 298 K

%AcOH	25	40	50	60	72
10 ⁴ <i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	453	174	89.1	44.3	16.2

solvent mixture (Table 4).

The isokinetic plot between activation enthalpies and entropies of oxidation of the eleven oximes is not very good (*r*² = 0.9144). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated^{14,15} from this plot is 334 ± 34. However, according to Exner¹⁶, an isokinetic relationship between the calculated values of enthalpies and entropies of activation is often vitiated by the random experimental errors associated with them. Exner¹⁶ has suggested an alternative method of testing the validity of isokinetic relationship. An Exner's plot between log *k*₂ at 288 K and log *k*₂ at 318 K is linear (*r*² = 0.9993). The value of isokinetic temperature is 482 ± 56 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of the activation.

Some conductivity measurements have been carried out to determine the nature of BTMACB in aqueous acetic acid solution¹⁷. It was observed that acetic acid has very low conductivity. Addition of BTMACB increases the conductivity of acetic acid. We measured the conductivity of BTMACB in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid (100–30%) and water also. We found that the conductivity increases sharply as the water content is initially increased but reaches a limiting value in about 60% acetic acid-water mixture. Therefore,

BTMACB can be considered as an ionic compound, which exists under our reaction conditions as benzyltrimethylammonium and chlorobromate ions [eq. (4)]. No effect of added benzyltrimethylammonium ion also indicates that the equilibrium (2) lies far towards the right.

The following equilibria may also exist in the solution.

The probable oxidising species in a solution of BTMACB are, therefore, chlorobromate ion, molecular bromine or hypobromous acid. The equilibria (3) and (4) are likely to be suppressed by the addition of BTMACl or potassium bromide. The absence of any added BTMACl and bromide ion on the reaction rate rules out the role of Br₂ and HOBr in the oxidation process. The oxidation of benzyl alcohol by bromine, in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, is retarded by the addition of bromide ions¹⁸ whereas the oxidation by BTMACB is unaffected by bromide ions. This indicates that in the present reaction bromine is not the active oxidizing species. Similar results were obtained in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by BTMACB¹⁶. Thus in the present reaction also the reactive oxidising species is the chlorobromate ion.

Solvent composition effect : The increase in the rate of oxidation with an increase in the polarity of the medium

Table 5. Reaction constants for the oxidative deoxygenation of aliphatic aldoximes by BTMACB^a

Temp. (K)	ρ*	δ	<i>R</i> ²	sd	ψ
278	0.54 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.02	0.9999	0.001	0.011
288	0.48 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.01	0.9989	0.002	0.038
298	0.42 ± 0.01	0.79 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.001	0.016
318	0.35 ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.007	0.011

^aNumber of compounds is 6.

suggests that the transition state is more polar than the reactants. The solvent effect was analysed using Grunwald-Winstein equation¹⁹,

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + mY \quad (5)$$

The plot of $\log k_2$ versus Y is linear ($r^2 = 0.9997$) with $m = 0.78 \pm 0.01$. The value of m suggests a transition state which is more polar than the reactants. Thus considerable charge separation takes place in the transition state of the reaction.

Correlation analysis of reactivity : We could not find any report about the mechanism of the reaction between a C=N bond and a polyhalogen derivative. Olefinic bonds are not usually subjected to nucleophilic attack. However, carbon-nitrogen double bonds, being dipolar in nature can easily be attacked by a nucleophile. The data in Table 1 showed that the rate of oxidation of ketoximes is much less as compared to that of the aldoximes. The reason for the slower reaction of ketoximes must be steric. As the central carbon changes from a trigonal to a tetrahedral state, the crowding around it increases. This increase in the steric crowding will be more in the case of ketoximes as compared to that in aldoximes. This observation is supported by the correlation analysis of the reactivity of the aliphatic aldo- and ketoximes also. The rate of oxidation of the aliphatic oximes did not yield significant correlation separately with Taft's σ^* and E_s values. The rates were, therefore, correlated with Pavelich-Taft's dual substituent-parameter equation²⁰,

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \Sigma \sigma^* + \delta \Sigma E_s + \log k_0$$

The rates exhibited excellent correlations in terms of the Pavelich-Taft equation (Table 5), the reaction constants being positive,

$$\log k_2 = 0.69 \pm 0.45 \sigma^* - 2.09 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.3679, \text{ sd} = 0.49, n = 6, \psi = 0.87, \text{Temp.} = 298 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.84 \pm 0.15 E_s - 1.98 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8922, \text{ sd} = 0.20, n = 6, \psi = 0.36, \text{Temp.} = 298 \text{ K}$$

Mechanism :

The observed low positive polar reaction constant, in the present reaction, points to a cyclic transition state in which the formation of the bond between chlorobromate-bromine and the carbon is somewhat ahead of the formation of N-Br bond. This supports a nucleophilic attack by a chlorobromate ion on the carbon. The positive steric

reaction constant points to a steric hindrance by the substituents. Therefore, the following mechanism (Scheme 1) is proposed for the reaction. The mechanism is supported by the values of activation parameters also. The

Scheme 1

low values of enthalpy of activation indicate that the bond-cleavage and bond-formation are almost synchronous. The large negative entropies of activation supports the formation of a rigid cyclic activated complex from two acyclic molecules.

Increase in the reaction rate with a decrease in the polarity of the solvent also supports a reaction involving a neutral species and an anion in the rate-determining step. As the oxime and the chlorobromate ion combine to form the complex, the charge density obviously decreases. Therefore, the formation of the activated complex is facilitated by a decrease in the polarity of the medium.

Hydroxynitrene (N-OH) has been recently reported as a very reactive intermediate²¹.

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